

Sustainability of University Lecturers' Performance for Actualization of Knowledge-Based Economy in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to find out the influence of sustainability of university Lecturers' performance on the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State, Nigeria. Two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The ex-post-facto design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 28,968 lecturers from the two public universities in Cross River State. Sampling was done in multiple stages using stratified, proportionate and simple random techniques and Yamane (1967) formula to generously draw a sample of 450 respondents. The instrument for the study was the Sustainability of University Lecturers' Performance and Actualization of Knowledge-Based Economy Questionnaire (SUTPAKEQ) developed in line with a Likert 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was duly validated by two experts in the departments of Educational Test and Measurement, and Educational Management of the University of Calabar. To determine the internal consistency of the instrument, a pilot test was carried out and the reliability coefficient based on Cronbach Alpha statistic obtained for the subscales range from .76 to .82. The data obtained from the field were analysed using a one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at the .05 level of significance. The results showed that the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State is influenced by University Lecturers' Performance Pay (Incentives) and University Lecturers' Performance evaluation. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that: University Lecturers' Performance incentives should be adequately and regularly paid to enhance their efficiency for the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State.

Keywords: Actualization, knowledge-based economy, lecturers' performance, sustainability, university.

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Introduction

Nigeria aspires to be in the commonwealth of the 20 leading economies in the world by the year 2020. This aspiration emerged on the realization that the endowment of Nigeria in material and human resources placed her in a good position to achieve this greatness. UNDP (2008), in

her Human Development Report, revealed that Nigeria is still at a low level of human development compared to countries in emerging economies. This is because the knowledge base of her citizenry which shapes the economic prosperity is infinitesimal. A knowledge-based economy is based on the utilisation of the outputs of the knowledge system to create new products and services through innovation.

Collaborating, Salmi (2016) noted that knowledge is indispensable not only for economic growth but also for social development purposes. Countries without a minimum institutional, scientific and technological capacity to apply research results are likely to lag in realizing key social and human benefits such as increased life expectancy, lower infant mortality, and improved health, nutrition, and sanitation. Such countries will be increasingly vulnerable to emerging environmental threats. Cooke and Leydesdorff (2006) said that a knowledge-based economy gives credence to the production and management of knowledge. For Powell and Snellman (2004), in Salem (2014), a knowledge-based economy makes use of knowledge as a fundamental tool in the accumulation of wealth, stimulating productivities, boosting economic growth, and creating employment. Besides the development of knowledge products, some countries relate a knowledge-based economy to higher education and research.

Universities are the main instruments of society for the constant pursuit of knowledge. Therefore, from kindergarten to post-university education, education is the principal means for the dissemination of knowledge in society. As a result of the drive towards knowledge societies internationally, interest in juvenile's education, particularly university education increased, as evidenced by the launch of several educational programmes among which are the NNPC scholarship award and Street Priest in the University of Calabar-Nigeria. Anninos (2007) pointed out that the primary aim of a university system is to enhance institutional improvement through quality assurance in every process and action, provision of performance information to the state and all interested parties. Miankheil, Nawaz, Khan and Wajidi (2012) further revealed that university plays an important role in our societies: It educates students for work or for academic and research performance which enhance knowledge development.

Kefela (2010) stressed that University education is a key to empowering Nigerians to acquire the right attitudes, skills and knowledge that would propel the achievement of vision 2020. Based on this premise, Finegold (2006) maintained that Universities educate young people to prepare them to be informed citizens, to have successful careers, and eventually to assume leadership roles in for-profit, non-profit, and government organizations; their faculties produce new knowledge that informs the education of future generations and reinforces technological progress. Universities are the source of strength in the knowledge-based economy of the twenty-first century. They are increasingly viewed as key drivers of innovation and foremost instruments of economic growth. Hence, Wolfe and Bramwell (2008) revealed that many educational managers considered research universities as knowledge factories for the new economy with mainly unutilized reservoirs of potentially commercialize knowledge waiting to be engaged by corporations. Wolfe (2005) contended that the mere presence of leading research universities in a region does not mean that they will trigger economic growth in the region despite being critical assets for such regional or urban economies.

Halepota and Irani (2010) stated that specific core competencies which define behaviours, skills, attributes, performance factors and proficiencies that every university teacher is expected to possess and display, determines the extent of the development of the knowledge-based economy. World Bank (2012) reported that one of the challenges for education quality which affects knowledge development is low teacher motivation and effort. Mbiti, Muralidharan, Romero, Schipper, Manda and Rajini (2019) found that the lecturers' performance pay programme provided cash bonuses to lecturers based on the performance of their students on independent learning assessments. That, lecturers' salaries were paid directly by the government and did not pass through the schools. That the number of students passing exams was greater than in Incentive schools, as total programme spending in Combination schools was 3.5% greater than the sum of spending in input and incentive schools. The results on complementarities are robust to accounting for this additional expenditure This is because implementation costs were a much larger fraction of total costs in the incentive programme. Thus, spending all the money from the Combination program on incentives would enable the value of the incentives to be 3.45 times higher than provided under the incentives programme, hence ensuring improvement in the knowledge base of the economy.

Neal and Schanzenbach (2010) also found that since the incentive formula rewarded lecturers based on the number of students who passed a threshold, lecturers in incentive and combination schools may have focused more on students near the passing threshold. This knowledge when utilizes properly by the students will boost the knowledge base of the economy. Fryer (2013) conducted an experiment that gave some lecturers' individual-based award bonuses and other lecturers fixed cash pay-outs before the school year that were then required to be returned if performance was low. They find no significant impacts from the first group, but they do find improvements from the second group suggesting that loss aversion is a more powerful incentive than standard pay-for-performance. Imberman and Lovernheim (2013) suggested that workers respond less to group incentives when they are part of a larger group but increasingly productive as their financial incentives become stronger.

Salmi (2016) stated that Incentives may affect the performance of existing lecturers: Thus, a fixed salary schedule very likely leads to lower quality of instruction for a given cost. First, subject differences in alternative career opportunities raise questions about the absence of salary differences across subjects. Second, evidence that finds a positive effect of pay for performance on student outcomes suggests that more widespread use of such incentives could elevate the quality of instruction. Hence, teacher salaries, job advancement and in some cases, employers are only weakly related to classroom performance in many school systems. Output-based pay is best used when output is well defined. He concluded that performance pay incentives are more likely to have significant and positive effects on the quality of instruction in the presence of relatively weak teacher professionalism, relatively large bonus size, focused performance metrics, fair performance metrics, and rewards linked to prior-period results.

Cano-Hurtado, Carot-Sierra, Fernández-Prada and Fargueta (n.d.) stressed that the evaluation of teaching activity is important for universities, as guaranteeing the quality of their

studies means assuring not only the professional skills of their teaching staff but also the quality of the teaching-learning. The teaching activity which is the object of evaluation is the teaching-learning process, carried out both inside and outside the classroom, and aids students' learning concerning the objectives and aptitudes defined in study curricula. Stroebe (2016) points out that, initially, lecturers' performance evaluation was intended to helping lecturers to improve their teaching, and later, it has been used to make important decisions on staff hiring and dismissal, promotions and salary determination; in any case, it will have to be considered whether the evaluation is used as a way to better influence learning (formative evaluation) or as a way to rate, reward, or punish performance (summative evaluation).

Silva, Lobo, Pereira and Duraó (2017) carried out a study on evaluation of teaching performance in higher education: students' perspectives and teaching management indicators. Descriptive analysis (frequency analysis, descriptive measures and association measures) and inferential analysis (ANOVA one-way, MANOVA one-way, MANOVA two-way and correlation analysis) were used for data analysis. Results showed that there was no correlation between the lecturers and the number of Curricular Units and the number of hours taught, there was no correlation between the number of years of service and the scientific area. The scientific area of the teacher does not influence the average evaluation of the teacher. Regarding the work area, this does not influence the average evaluation of the; And in terms of the number of years of service, this does not influence the student's appreciation of the teacher's ability to stimulate the motivation and interest of students; As for the department, it has no influence on the student's appreciation of the teacher's ability to provide materials to support the study and on the teacher's ability to comply with the evaluation rules agreed with the students; about the number of curricular units taught and the number of hours taught does not influence the student's appreciation of the teacher's commitment to promoting the quality of teaching.

Taylor and Tyler (n.d.) found that lecturers are more productive during the school year when they are being evaluated, but even more productive in the years after evaluation. A student taught by a lecturer after that teacher has been through the Cincinnati evaluation will score about 10 per cent of a standard deviation higher in math than a similar student taught by the same teacher before the lecturers were evaluated. The purpose of the study was to find out the influence of sustainability of university Lecturers' performance on the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study aimed at:

1. Finding the influence of Lecturers' Performance Pay (Incentives) on actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State, Nigeria.
2. Determining the influence of Lecturers' performance evaluation on actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State, Nigeria

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. University lecturers' performance pay (Incentives) does not significantly influence the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State.
2. There is no significant influence of university lecturers' performance evaluation on the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State

Methods

The ex-post-facto design was adopted for the study. This is a methodical investigation where the researchers do not have direct control over the independent variables because their manifestations have long occurred and they are characteristically not manipulated (Isangedighi, Joshua, Asim and Ekuri, 2004). In this study, the ex-post-facto design was apt because the manipulation of such variables as lecturers' Performance Pay and lecturers' evaluation was impossible in the course of this study. They have already interacted to produce the level of actualization of a knowledge-based economy which the researchers only measured.

The population of the study was 9,456 lecturers out of which the University of Cross River State, Calabar having 524 and the University of Calabar, Calabar with 8,932 (Directorates of Academic Planning, Calabar, 2021). Sampling was done in multiple stages using stratified, proportionate and simple random techniques: University of Calabar, Calabar and Cross River University of Technology, Calabar were first stratified into two; the proportionate procedure was further used to draw a sample of 425 respondents and 25 respondents from University of Calabar, Calabar and Cross River University of Technology, Calabar respectively making a total sample of 450 which were randomly selected from the institutions. Yamane (1967) formula was also used to generously draw this sample of 450 respondents from the population.

The instrument for the study was Sustainability of University Lecturers' Performance and Actualization of Knowledge-Based Economy Questionnaire (SULPAKEQ) developed in line with a Likert 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with a weight of 4, 3, 2, and 1 for all positively worded items and weight of 1, 2, 3, and 4 for all negatively worded items respectively. The instrument was duly faced validated by two experts in the departments of Educational Test and Measurement, and Educational Management of the University of Calabar. To determine the internal consistency of the instrument, a pilot test was carried out and the reliability coefficient based on Cronbach Alpha statistic obtained for the subscales range from .76 to .82. The data obtained from the field were analyzed using a one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at the .05 level of significance.

Results

The results for the test of hypotheses are presented hypothesis-by-hypothesis as follows:

Hypothesis 1

University lecturers' Performance Pay (Incentives) does not significantly influence the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State. To test this hypothesis, a One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied with university lecturers' Performance Pay (Incentives) as the independent variable or factor and actualization of a knowledge-based economy as the dependent variable. The f-ratio was used to test the overall influence and the

Fishers Least Significant Difference (LSD) test to compare pairs of means as a post hoc test. The ANOVA results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: One-way ANOVA of influence of University Lecturers' Performance Pay (Incentives) on actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State, Nigeria

University Lecturers' Performance Pay	N	Mean	SD
Prompt Salary	35	12.53	1.43
Leave grant	50	12.22	1.53
Overtime allowance	215	12.50	0.99
Promotion arrears	26	12.19	1.16
Hazards allowance	124	12.54	1.41
Total	450	12.40	1.31

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F	p
Between groups	294.61	4	73.65	9.71*	.01
Within groups	3451.21	455	7.59		
Total	3745.82	449			

*Significant at .05 level, $P < .05$

From Table 1, the mean showed that university lecturers who were paid overtime hazards allowance were the highest ($\bar{x} = 12.54$), followed by those who were paid a prompt salary ($\bar{x} = 12.53$) while the least were those that were paid promotion arrears ($\bar{x} = 12.19$). The p-value ($\bar{x} = .01$) associated with the computed F-value of 9.710 was observed to be less than .05. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that university lecturers' performance pay (Incentives) significantly influence the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State. To find out which pair of means was responsible for the observed significant results, Fisher's LSD test was carried out. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: LSD Pairwise comparison of the influence of University Lecturers' Performance Pay (Incentives) on actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State, Nigeria

University Lecturers' Performance Pay	Prompt salary	Leave grant	Hazards allowance	Promotion arrears	Overtime allowance
prompt salary	11.13**	.37	.51*	.05	.32*
Leave grant	.06	11.58	.09*	.48*	.48
Hazards allowance	.01	.00	11.54	.08	.04*
Promo arrears	.06	.03	.05	11.27	.49
Overtime allowance	.00	.06	.00	.05	11.85

*Significant at .05 level

**Values along the main diagonal are group means, above it is the mean difference (MD) and below it are corresponding p-values

The results in Table 2 showed that the mean (\bar{x}) of university lecturers who were paid prompt salary were significantly different from those who were paid hazards allowance (MD= .507, $P = .010 < .05$), and those who were paid overtime (MD= .321, $P = .001 < .05$). Those who were paid leave grant were also significantly different from those who were paid hazard allowance (MD= .093, $P = .000 < .05$) and those who were paid promotion allowance (MD= .477, $P = .032 < .05$). University lecturers who were paid hazards allow were significantly

different from those who were paid overtime (MD= .035, P= .004 < .05), and all the other paired companions were not significant.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of university lecturers' performance evaluation on the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State. To test this hypothesis, a One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied with university lecturers' Performance evaluation as the independent variable or factor and actualization of a knowledge-based economy as the dependent variable. The f-ratio was used to test the overall influence and the Fishers Least Significant Difference (LSD) test to compare pairs of means as a post hoc test. The ANOVA results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: One-way ANOVA of influence of University Lecturers' Performance evaluation on actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State, Nigeria

University Lecturers' Performance evaluation	N	Mean	SD
Summative evaluation	177	10.16	.97
Formative evaluation	205	10.00	1.00
Self-evaluation	12	10.09	1.00
Students' evaluation	50	10.12	.96
Peer co-evaluation	6	10.11	.91
Total	450	10.08	.97

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F-ratio	p
Between groups	273.35	4	68.34	10.17*	.00
Within groups	3056.86	455	6.72		
Total	3330.22	449			

*Significant at .05 level, P < .05

From Table 3, the mean showed that the Summative evaluation of university lecturers was the best (\bar{x} = 10.160), followed by Students' evaluation of university lecturers (\bar{x} = 10.12) while the least was the formative evaluation of university lecturers (\bar{x} = 10.00). The p-value of .000 associated with the computed F-value of 10.17 was observed to be less than .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that University Lecturers' Performance evaluation significantly influence the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State. To find out which pair of means was responsible for the observed significant results, Fisher's LSD test was carried out. The results are presented in Table 4.

The results on Table 4 showed that the mean (x) of university lecturers who had summative evaluation were significantly different from those who had formative evaluation (MD = .22, p = .00 < .05), students' evaluation (MD = .23, p = .001 < .05) and peer co-evaluation (MD = .200, p = .01 < .05). Those who had formative evaluation were also significantly different from those who had self-evaluation (MD= .21, p = .01 < .05) and peer co-evaluation (MD = .36, p = .00 < .05). while those who were Self-evaluated were significantly different from those that were evaluated by students (MD = .21, p = .01 < .05). and all the other paired companions were not significant.

Table 4: LSD Pairwise comparison of the influence of University Lecturers' Performance evaluation on actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State, Nigeria

University Lecturers' Performance eval	Summative evaluation	Formative evaluation	Self-evaluation	Students' evaluation	Peer evaluation	co-evaluation
Summative evaluation	11.41**	.224*	.28	.23*	.20*	
Formative evaluation	.00	11.42	.21*	.30	.36*	
Self-evaluation	.05	.01	11.93	.21*	.27	
Students' evaluation	.00	.05	.01	11.59	.22	
Peer co-evaluation	.01	.00	.05	.00	11.33	

*Significant at .05 level, $P < .05$

**Values along the main diagonal are group means, above it are the mean differences (MD) and below it are the corresponding P-value

Discussion

The results of hypothesis one pointed out that University Lecturers' Performance Pay (Incentives) significantly influence actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State as the P-value (.008) associated with the computed F-value (9.710) is less than .05. This study aligned with Neal and Schanzenbach (2010) who found that since the incentive formula rewarded lecturers based on the number of students who passed a threshold, lecturers in Incentive and Combination schools may have focused more on students near the passing threshold. This knowledge when utilized properly by the students will boost the knowledge base of the economy. Fryer (2013) conducted an experiment that gave some lecturers' individual-based award bonuses and other lecturers fixed cash pay-outs before the school year that were then required to be returned if performance was low. They find no significant impacts from the first group, but they do find improvements from the second group suggesting that loss aversion is a more powerful incentive than standard pay-for-performance. Imberman and Lovernheim (2013) suggested that workers respond less to group incentives when they are part of a larger group but increasingly productive as their financial incentives become stronger.

Salmi (2016) stated that Incentives may affect the performance of existing lecturers: Thus, a fixed salary schedule very likely leads to lower quality of instruction for a given cost. First, subject differences in alternative career opportunities raise questions about the absence of salary differences across subjects. Second, evidence that finds a positive effect of pay for performance on student outcomes suggests that more widespread use of such incentives could elevate the quality of instruction. Hence, teacher salaries, job advancement and in some cases, employers are only weakly related to classroom performance in many school systems. Output-based pay is best used when output is well defined. The results of hypothesis two revealed that University Lecturers' Performance evaluation significantly influence the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State as the p-value (.000) associated with the computed F-value (10.172) was less than .05. This result is in agreement with Cano-Hurtado, Carot-Sierra, Fernández-Prada and Fargueta (n.d.) who stressed that the evaluation of teaching activity is important for universities, as guaranteeing the quality of their studies means assuring

not only the professional skills of their teaching staff but also the quality of the teaching-learning. The teaching activity which is the object of evaluation is the teaching-learning process, carried out both inside and outside the classroom, and aids students' learning with respect to the objectives and aptitudes defined in study curricula.

Stroebe (2016) points out that, initially, lecturers' performance evaluation was intended to helping lecturers to improve their teaching, and later, it has been used to make important decisions on staff hiring and dismissal, promotions and salary determination; in any case, it will have to be considered whether an evaluation is used as a way to better influence learning (formative evaluation) or as a way to rate, reward, or punish performance (summative evaluation). This study is at variance with Silva, Lobo, Pereira and Duraó (2017) who showed that there was no correlation between the lecturers and the number of Curricular Units and the number of hours taught, there was no correlation between the number of years of service and the scientific area. The scientific area of the teacher does not influence the average evaluation of the teacher. Regarding the work area, this does not influence the average evaluation of the; In reference to the number of Curricular Units taught and the number of hours taught does not influence the student's appreciation of the teacher's commitment to promoting the quality of teaching. Taylor and Tyler (n.d.) found that lecturers are more productive during the school year when they are being evaluated, but even more productive in the years after evaluation. A student taught by a lecturer after that lecturer has been through the evaluation will score about 10 per cent of a standard deviation higher in math than a similar student taught by the same teacher before the lecturers were evaluated.

Conclusion

A knowledge-based economy is an economy that is capable of knowledge production, dissemination and use; where knowledge is a key factor in growth, wealth creation and employment, and where human capital is the driver of creativity, innovation and generation of new ideas, with reliance on information and communication technology as an enabler. This study revealed that the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State is influenced by University Lecturers' Performance Pay (Incentives) and University Lecturers' Performance evaluation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. University Lecturers' Performance incentives should be adequately and regularly paid to enhance their efficiency for the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State.

2. University Lecturers' Performance evaluation should be periodically carried out to ascertain their proficiency for the actualization of a knowledge-based economy in Cross River State.

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